

COMMUNITY EMPOWERMENT MODEL ANALYSIS ON MOUNT SINABUNG POST-ERUPTION REHABILITATION AND RECONSTRUCTION PROCESS IN INDONESIA

HARMENSYAH¹, BAMBANG SUPRIYONO², MR. KHAIRUL MULUK³ and FIRDA HIDAYATI⁴

^{1,2,3,4} Brawijaya University, Malang, Indonesia.

Email: ¹harmensyahfia@gmail.com; ²bambangspkamelia@gmail.com; ³mrkhairulmuluk@ub.ac.id;

⁴hidayat.ub@gmail.com;

Abstract

This study aims to see the community development process in the relocation of mount Sinabung eruption in Karo, Indonesia. Stage two of the Mount Sinabung Post-Eruption Rehabilitation and Reconstruction policy in Karo Regency, North Sumatra, Indonesia as a self-relocation process is evaluated. After the Mount Sinabung eruption, the residents of the area prepared the land on their own to build homes. Prior to the building of the house, TPRM (Tim Pendamping Relokasi Mandiri) provided mentorship services. Self-relocation policy imposed a number of difficulties on disaster-affected populations, including environmental, social, economic, vocational, and cultural changes. Mount Sinabung's empowerment paradigm in Karo Regency, Indonesia, was the focus of this descriptive-qualitative study. Self-relocation was employed by the groups. Observations, interviews, and documentation were used to gather information. In the wake of a natural disaster, communities were found to have implemented a number of important strategies and ideas. There were three guiding principles: (1) a high level of community optimism about post-disaster recovery; (2) a tendency for communities to live in groups; and (3) a community's ability to strengthen each other and increase its own potential. Physical and non-physical security was provided to the communities by the government. Community empowerment's ultimate goal is to develop an autonomous society and increase life quality over time, which is why the post-disaster effort adheres to this ultimate purpose.

Keywords: Self-relocation, Empowerment, Post-Disaster

Introduction

This study examines the evaluation of community based development project conducted in the community of volcano disaster in Karo, Sumatera Indonesia. The purposes are to see the community development strategies conducted by the Indonesian government and other stakeholders during the engagements. Mount Sinabung has been inert for 400 years, according to the Pusat Vulkanologi dan Mitigasi Bencana Geologi (PVMBG). The volcano had previously erupted around 1600 (Febriaty, 20015). Because of the long time interval between eruptions, the residents of the area never had seen a volcanic explosion. Community and government were unprepared when Mount Sinabung erupted in 2010. The Karo Regency government responded by forming the Badan Penanggulangan Bencana Daerah (BPBD) (Suri, 2015). The formation of the BPBD was intended to bridge the execution of disaster management in Karo Regency. Between 2010 and 2015, the Sinabung volcano's status changed from SIAGA to AWAS. PVMBG's DANGER is the highest level volcano early warning system (Gunawan et al., 2019; Pallister et al., 2019). During the study period, Mount

Sinabung's activity did not decrease. Mount Sinabung emitted hot clouds up to 5,000 meters on March 2, 2021. At 11:00 AM, Mount Sinabung emitted 1,000 meters of volcanic ash.

The eruption of Mount Sinabung in Karo Regency affected agriculture, tourism, ecology, infrastructure, economics, and the social community (Hafni and Lubis, 2016; Nainggolan et al., 2019; Sinaga, Sembiring, and Lubis, 2015). Economic growth, social connections, poverty, and livelihoods may all be affected by volcanic eruptions, according to Blanco et al. As a result, urgent action is needed to restore social and economic activity. A disaster-affected community's basic requirements must be met; inhabitants who cannot return home must be offered other homes; and residents coming home must be given enough care and safe handling.

Relocation is important in light of the current scenario. The relocation policy necessitates careful consideration of a wide range of factors to ensure recovery. Building Back Better principles must guide the relocation policy (Khasalamwa, 2009; Mannakkara, Wilkinson, and Potangaroa, 2018). Those fleeing a volcanic eruption may be able to relocate to a new place that is less likely to be affected by the ash. However, relocation is a lengthy process that requires careful planning and mapping. A large number of refugees and the availability of land and resources necessitate a gradual relocation procedure.

Specifically, the purpose of this study was to characterize and determine the Mount Sinabung community's post-eruption empowerment model in the Karo Regency. Additionally, this research sought to uncover how the community was able to freely empower itself, recover, and thrive following the eruption, from the perspectives of economic, social, and cultural factors. It is vital to remember that the self-relocation policy in Indonesia is a very recent development.

Research Question

To guide the research process, the following research question is sought to answer: "What is the community empowerment model of the self-relocation policy in Mount Sinabung eruption-affected areas?"

Literature Review

Post Disaster Recovery

Post-Disaster Recovery is a process that aims to address social issues such as inequality and poverty, minimize the vulnerability of the people as a result of catastrophes, and achieve long-term sustainable development (He, 2019). Post-Disaster Recovery is typically defined as an effort to restore a post-disaster situation to a state that is acceptable to the community. It emphasizes the provision of immediate remedies in order to restore a sense of normalcy to impacted populations as soon as feasible (Khasalamwa, 2009). It goes through a complicated and dynamic decision-making process with a wide range of stakeholders and participants (Mannakkara, Wilkinson, and Potangaroa, 2018). Creating a resilient future via community

empowerment is the goal of post-disaster recovery efforts; as such, it is essential that communities adhere to the Build Back Better principles (Mannakkara, Wilkinson, and Potangaroa, 2018)

According to Ingram et al. (2006), one of the most difficult challenges in post-disaster recovery planning is resolving the contradiction between short-term and long-term concerns. When it comes to restoring community security and preserving livelihoods, short-term recovery is critical and must occur quickly. When it comes to long-term recovery, the emphasis is on rebuilding during the years following a tragedy. For post-disaster recovery efforts to be successful, it is necessary to do a need analysis and surveys in order to understand the local context of the disaster-affected community in order to provide suitable assistance (Khasalamwa, 2009). The government may assess the requirements of the community and make adjustments as necessary. Several parties are involved in the recovery decisions (Ballano et al. n.d.).

When we talk about good recovery, we're talking about top-to-bottom policy implementation. The community's needs and capabilities must also be taken into consideration during the recovery process (Berke et al., 1993). Involvement of citizens and local leaders in policy-making is a valuable source of local data. After a crisis, there is an opportunity to find solutions to other issues in the community. In order to rebuild the economy, enhance living standards, and strengthen the economy and social welfare, it must be viewed as continuing rather than only temporary reconstruction of housing. An effective and efficient post-disaster recovery solution is necessary as part of the Build Back Better principles, according to Mannakkara, Wilkinson, and Potangaroa (2018). Stakeholder management by selecting an acceptable institutional framework, proper post-disaster laws and regulation, and a monitoring and evaluation mechanism are three ways to improve the efficiency and effectiveness of Build Back Better principles. All parties and stakeholders need to be involved in the post-recovery phase.

Community-Based Empowerment

As an individual process, empowerment reduces people's powerlessness and dependency, allowing them to take greater responsibility for the decisions they make (Islam, 2016). As a contrast to the empowerment idea, community support and integration that places an emphasis on informal support networks as well as community psychology are also available (Sarason, 1988). In the context of empowerment, this process may be referred to as recovery. To recover from an addiction, it is necessary to change one's outlook on life, as well as his or her outlook on the world around them (Anthony, 1993). Recovery, like empowerment, is an individual process that progresses through various stages, such as the transition from dependency to independence. The goal of recovery is to give people more power over their own life (Lord, Nelson, and Ochocka 2016).

According to Tengland (2008), the empowerment notion can be used in two ways: as an end goal and as a method or strategy. Control over the factors that influence a person's well-being is what it means to achieve this goal. It refers to the process of establishing a business

partnership. The customer or community is in charge of making the modifications, so they decide on their own what they should be and how they should be used. For example, Melkote and Steeves (2015) argued that empowerment phenomena can be employed to strengthen societal transformation, or to help people overcome their own limitations (Dew n.d.; Hooley and Miklowitz 2018; Jennings et al. 2012). Consequently, the term "empowerment" refers to the relationship between a subject and an object. Friedman (1992) categorized community empowered decision-making into three (3) sorts of powers: social, political, and psychological. Access to a household's production base, such as knowledge, skills and financial resources is referred to as social power. Individual family members' access to a decision-making process, particularly ones that influence their future, is a key component of political power. An individual's psychological strength can be exhibited by their confident demeanor. Success in social politics results in psychological empowerment. Self-respect and mutual respect are the foundations of self-empowerment. Empowerment is a process in which people help each other and accept responsibility for their decisions and actions (Rodwell, 1996). As a result, empowerment serves as a means to unlock the full potential of a person.

Community empowerment can be defined in three ways: (1) to enable or create an environment or climate conducive to prospective community development, (2) to empower or strengthen community potential, and (3) to protect, with empowerment serving as a form of protection (Kartasasmita, 1997). Kirschenbaum (2004) discusses catastrophe preparedness in terms of supply, skill level, planning, and protection. Supply refers to the availability of necessary physical items in the event of a disaster, assuming that basic services are unavailable. Individual skills refer to the knowledge and abilities necessary to save lives or care for the injured. Plans are a term that refers to preparedness from a family organizing standpoint. Protection is a term that refers to the physical means used to safeguard persons and family members against external hazards. Post-disaster empowerment and community empowerment are synonymous terms—both have an impact on persons and the environment.

Challenges of Self-relocation Rehabilitation and Reconstruction

Mount Sinabung was classified as a type-A volcano by the authorities (Gunawan et al., 2019). As a result of the Mount Sinabung eruption, the authorities chose to remove its residents (Manurung and Trimurni, 2020). Transferring a portion or all of a business's operations, infrastructure and support services from one location to another are known as "relocation." There are several reasons for relocating a piece of equipment. As long as the original and new communities and infrastructures are linked, relocation is still possible (Iuchi and Mutter, 2020; Pandia, Rachmawati, and Mei, 2016). The relocation process was broken down into three steps by the government. People from three villages were relocated in the first stage of relocation (112 households of Bekerah Village, 128 households of Sukameriah Village, and 130 households of Simacem Village). Households from four villages were relocated in Stage II (778 households of Gurukinayan Village, 109 households of Kutatonggal Village, 611 households of Berastepu Village, and 185 households of Gamber Village). It took 648 families from four communities to relocate in Stage III (125 households of Jeraya Village, 150 households of Kuta Tengah Village, 76 households of Pintu Besi

Village, and 297 households of Tiga Pancur Village). After a successful first stage of relocation, every family was given new homes and fields. After the first stage of relocation was completed, the second stage of relocation followed.

According to the Karo Regent's Decree of June 10, 2016, the Bantuan Dana Rumah (BDR) and/or the Farming Business Funds (BDLUT) for the self-relocation of Gurukinayan Villagers were adhered to throughout the second stage of relocation. Karo Regency residents in Berastepu, Kuta Tonggal, and Gamber were affected by the Mount Sinabung eruption disaster. Nearly 2,000 people were served by the initiative, which was made up of 1,682 homes from four villages: 778 from Gurukinayan, 108 from Kuto Tonggal, and 611 from Berastepu. In the Siosar region, the third stage of relocation was completed. Relocation Stage III relocated 1,127 households from the villages of Sigarang-Garang, Sukanalu, Mardinding, and Lau Kawar.

Relocation Stage II was carried out by the Karo Regency Government for populations affected by the Mount Sinabung eruption. The procedure, however, was slightly different. Both residential sites and agricultural fields were sought by the community. To boost safety, feasibility, and legal aspects, the government should provide both residential areas and agricultural land to comply to the relocation concept by shifting sections or full activities, facilities, and infrastructure from one location to another. However, Relocation Stage II encountered difficulties, such as obtaining a permit from the Forestry Department, despite the fact that the Central Government had allocated funds to the community. As a result, the community urged that the Karo Regency administration outline action plans as soon as possible. As a result, the Karo Regency government revised its policies and action plans, renaming the Relocation Stage II strategy Relokasi Mandiri (Self-Relocation). The notion of self-relocation relates to the ability of communities affected by the Mount Sinabung eruption to prepare lands for residential areas on their own. As a precondition, TPRM provided mentoring during the housing development process.

Self-relocation has had an impact on the community since it allows residents to thrive independently from economic, social and cultural standpoints following a natural disaster. It was a difficult procedure for the Karo Regency administration to restore local wisdom and community social network, as well as to adapt to new farming patterns, community culture, and employment type in the new places. (Tony 2018). (Nainggolan, Hotden, Tampubolon, et al., 2019). The Karo Regency community has a well-established social network, particularly among the villages of the region. They treat their village neighbors as though they were part of their own family. As a result, the residents of the neighborhood planned to relocate as a group. For further clarification, the soil type of Mount Sinabung, which is suited for farming, does not necessitate additional costs for agricultural activities and maintenance. The community was forced to adapt to a new environment due to relocation. The community is in need of help because different soil types can affect agricultural yields in different ways. To achieve post-disaster rehabilitation and reconstruction policy objectives, community participation and empowerment are essential.

Methods

This study was descriptive in nature. The qualitative technique was adopted by the researchers. According to Creswell (2009), qualitative research is a method for exploring and comprehending the meaning derived from social or humanitarian problems. The qualitative research process included asking questions and procedures, collecting specific data from participants, inductively analyzing data from specific themes to general themes, and interpreting the data's meaning. The structure or framework of descriptive research is adaptable. Descriptive research necessitates an inductive research approach, focusing on individual meaning and translating a problem's complexity. Descriptive research provides a causal assessment based on the perspectives of those involved in the events under study—those people follow the chronological flow of events in the problems under study. The researchers are aware that the qualitative approach has the potential to serve as a conduit for obtaining unexpected results. Furthermore, in terms of developing new theoretical frameworks, the qualitative approach goes beyond preconceived notions and frameworks. The researchers gathered data through interviews with members of the affected community, stakeholders, and local officials, as well as observations in affected villages and new residential areas. Data analysis was carried out using an interactive model developed by Miles, Huberman, and Saldana (2014), which included data collection, data processing, data presentation, and drawing conclusions.

Findings and Discussion

Impacts and Challenges

As a result of the Karo people's willingness to relocate when the government provided agricultural land, the relocation program is problematic. Housing and agricultural land funds were provided by the government. Because of this, the impacted community was able to rebuild on its own. It was decided that Relocation Stage II would be a self-relocation policy because the government couldn't supply an adequate location. They built their own homes on territory that had been devastated by the Mount Sinabung eruption. Then, TPRM supervised the construction of the community's new homes as a condition.

According to an interview with affected communities, particularly those who self-relocated, the majority of respondents felt that the self-relocation program did not assist restore the economy to its full potential. There were various causes for the inefficient self-relocation. First, there had been unbalanced economic developments between the pre- and post-disaster periods. Second, it was assumed that aid in Siosar would be greater than self-relocation financing. Third, communities needed to build their own housing. Furthermore, individuals of the community may be segregated from their fellow villagers. These three considerations made self-relocation difficult to accomplish. In addition, community leaders and government cooperation are required to bridge the adaption gap.

Community Empowerment Patterns

In order to better understand the issue and develop a solution, the researchers used qualitative research. According to the majority of respondents, the community's economy was not restored by self-relocation. Some members of the community thought that the self-relocation concept was acceptable. To employ government funding, self-relocation gave the community the freedom and capacity to do so. However, the word "self-relocation" must be re-examined in the second stage of relocation. An economic, social, and cultural viewpoint on self-relocation shows that the community needs to take its own steps during the recovery process.

According to respondents' opinions, the church had a substantial influence. It urged the affected community to recover from the disaster by requesting that they relocate to other residential locations. The church carried out a number of programs and activities, such as giving basic foodstuffs, helping the people to settle in easily in their new residential area. The church also boosted the morale of the community through times of adversity and strengthened the community's mental state and awareness in order for them to recover. To recover faster, disaster-affected communities engaged in a variety of activities and jobs that maximized time, space, and possibilities. Individual capability must be increased in accordance with the self-relocation framework. To help the economy, members of the community took on a variety of jobs, including becoming farmers, agricultural laborers, traders, entrepreneurs, and odd-job employees. The occupations they took demonstrated a deep desire to rehabilitate and an inner incentive to do so. Self-relocation did not worsen the community's state; rather, it encouraged activity in the impacted community. As a result, the community recovers and improves.

Programs and activities were provided by the Karo Regency Government and other parties to help the disaster-affected community, such as training programs. Some of these training programs include creating chips (snacks), screen-printed organic fertilizer and pellet, weaving and honey-producing honey bee colonies. In spite of this, many programs and trainings did not run on a long-term basis and were discontinued. Thus, training equipment had to be retired. There was no thorough planning by the administration when it came to creating a training program. Because of this, the training program was unable to empower the local population.

Self-relocation Rehabilitation and Reconstruction Process

The goal of self-relocation in the context of community-based rehabilitation and reconstruction is to give settlement to disaster-affected populations in safer locales (Build Back Better and Safer). Better and safer implies that the settlements are environmentally friendly (technical, social, and legal). The settlement program must also have a lower long-term risk of disaster. Mount Sinabung post-eruption rehabilitation and reconstruction was divided into three stages: (1) relocation of three affected villages (Bekerah Village, Simacem Village, and Sukameriah Village) to Siosar (370 households); (2) independent relocation of four villages (1,682 households) (Berastepu Village, Gurukinayan Village, Gamber Village, and Kutatonggal Village); and (3) fulfillment of relocation needs for three villages and one

hamlet (1,038 households). The entire budget for repair and reconstruction was IDR 1,059,491,618,812.00.

"House for a house" and "land for land" are the most common forms of aid. As a reminder, the help is not compensation, but rather a sort of stimulus cash. As a result, more clarification and explanation is typically needed in order to avoid confusion. IDR 110,000,000.00 was set aside by the government for self-relocation funds in the form of a stimulus fund. IDR 59,400,000.00 for Lahan Tanah Rumah (LTR) and IDR 50,600,000.00 for Bantuan Dana Lahan Usaha Tani (BDLUT) were two forms of self-relocation support funding.

Budget provision for self-relocation was divided into funding assistance—for example, BDR and BDLUT. The government aided in the construction of homes and the acquisition of agricultural fields. One important part of self-relocation is ensuring the long-term viability of affected communities' livelihoods. As a result, the community must be granted land ownership. To avoid property disputes, land legality or ownership must have a sound legal foundation. Land legality has two fundamental functions: (1) it gives social and psychological security to the community, and (2) it deters new land disputes. However, the bulk of the population preferred to construct residences in groups. The Karo Regency culture demonstrates a deep bond between community members. In the home village, neighbors are considered family members. Following the establishment of the self-relocation policy, the community decided to build dwellings in groups. There were 28 self-relocation stations in Karo Regency, according to Badan Daerah Penanggulangan Bencana (BPBD). From an economic, social, and cultural standpoint, the community elected to work together as one group during the recovery process. Members of the community came together to help one another, allowing disaster-affected areas to heal, flourish, and prosper.

Agricultural and residential land constructions were also restricted by the government. There was a seven-kilometer minimum separation from Mount Sinabung and an eight-kilometer maximum separation from the Karo Regency's limits. During the construction of residential areas, the communities had to adhere to minimum standards, consider the environment, and use standard earthquake-resistant houses, such as double walls, stone foundations, and iron that was 12 millimeters in diameter and bent (40 degrees) for connecting reinforced concrete and beams. Buildings built using this technology would withstand natural disasters and keep the community safe. The government permitted the community to build their own homes, either on their own or with the help of third parties, in order to stress the community's sense of self-reliance. The government only set minimal guidelines and let the community decide on house types and designs. The community must make good use of the funds it has been given and abide by the terms of the collective bargaining agreement. Self-relocation technical instructions and rules were supplied by the government, as well as financial aid for residential and agricultural sectors. So, the community may be able to receive needed services as a means of recovery. Deterring Mount Sinabung and other disasters, the government provided the inhabitants with a decent and safe location to live.

Discussion

As a result of the Mount Sinabung eruption, the surrounding village implemented a self-relocation program. Environmental, social, economic, vocational, and cultural changes confronted the community. "The people require self-potential and products to deal with the numerous changes," one responder noted. Self-potential, or the ability to take actions and perform various jobs, is critical since it demonstrates a person's strong desire to speed up recovery. The government's responsibility is simply to guide the community." Members of the community with high self-esteem were able to heal and improve quickly. A strong will to heal and the skill to cultivate self-potential are required in addition to self-potential.

An interview with an informant revealed, "Before the disaster, I have done various types of work—farm laborer, odd jobs, and trading. I returned to farming afterward. I did this because I had a desire to recover". Providing assistance programs (financial aid and support assistance) and training were the actual efforts taken by the central and local governments to repair disaster-affected communities. Residential and agricultural land funding were part of the help program. Producing paving blocks and chips (a snack food) was one of the training programs offered, as was screen printing, organic fertilizers and pellets, weaving, and beekeeping as well. Program performance was subpar, though. In the opinion of a source, the government did not do a good job of mapping out the target population. As a result, things didn't go as planned during the training session. Many pieces of equipment were also rendered obsolete.

To expand and heal after migration, the community needs willingness, awareness, and self-potential—this is a new type of theoretical description developed by Kirschenbaum (2004), Kartasmita (1997), and Friedman (1992). According to Kirschenbaum (2004), supply refers to the availability of physical items required for practically every foreseeable calamity, assuming basic services are unavailable. However, rather than preparing for a prospective calamity, the community focused on supply availability as part of post-disaster rehabilitation. The term "availability" relates to both actual commodities and one's own potential. According to Kirschenbaum (2004), ability refers to an individual's competence level based on knowledge and talents to save lives or care for the injured. In practice, the community used its own resources to care for victims and rebuild the economy. The community demonstrated a tremendous desire to participate in various post-disaster initiatives. According to Friedman (1992), psychological power relates to demonstrated individual potential, such as confident behavior.

As a result of this, the government was unable to empower the people. In order for a community's potential to be realized, it is necessary to empower the people in the community (Kartasmita, 1997). Observational evidence suggests that the community's strong talents, rather than government initiatives, were responsible for the empowered recovery process.

Several parties were able to boost the capacity of each individual. The Karo regency's churches organized a variety of initiatives and activities to improve the mental health of disaster-stricken residents. Relocating communities were helped by church initiatives that

met their basic needs and made it easier for them to adjust to their new surroundings. Community empowerment, according to Kartasasmita (1997), establishes an atmosphere or climate in which the community's potential can grow. This would allow the community to concentrate on labor and repair the economy. However, community empowerment did not come from the government, but rather from the community and the churches.

Moving an existing residential neighborhood to a new place is referred to as self-relocation. The most important issue to consider is the security of the new location, thus thorough preparation is required. The disaster-affected community carefully planned its self-relocation through household discussions on emergency operational, location selection, environmental, and information issues, among other things. Planning yielded a powerful indicator for decision-making. Because Karo Regency has a strong community culture, most disaster-affected communities sought to build dwellings in groups during the self-relocation implementation. In the home village, neighbors are considered family members. As a result, the community elected to remain in groups during the development of the residential area. Karo Regency's BPBD recorded 28 self-relocation sites. From an economic, social, and cultural standpoint, the community elected to work together as one group during the recovery process. Members of the community came together to help one another, allowing disaster-affected areas to heal, flourish, and prosper.

Martin conveyed three crucial factors taken into consideration during relocation, stating that, "I provided direction to the community. Determining the self-relocation site requires three factors. First, not to fall under other people's influence. Second, look for areas near family or close relatives. Third, look for areas capable of supporting community potential. Therefore, allowing the community to develop".

Planning, according to Kirschenbaum (2004), is a person's ability to acquire information and knowledge. Afterwards, the individual works with the community or family to implement the plan. Community planning was carried out by homes, groups, and social groupings as a result of observation results. The residents of the area did more than just save aside money for an evacuation. New beginnings necessitated more extensive planning. Social power is defined by Friedman (1992) as having access to the information, expertise, skills, and financial resources necessary for the production of household goods and services. Social organizations like *runggu* (community conversation) were used by the community to carry out the recovery process, including budgeting, selection, and decision-making. The decision was made in the interest of restoring the community after a community discussion.

According to the parameters described above, the most important component for the disaster-affected community is protection. The community realized that migration was necessary to avert the potential of future disasters. The majority of community members chose a place with enough protection against disasters, land issues, and residency status. Martin stated that, "There are two contexts of protection. First, protection against disaster. The government makes technical guidelines and action plans to deter the threat. Second, protection of the status of residence. Other communities may not receive the relocated communities well."

Preparation for disasters is a critical factor that must take precedence above anything else. The goal of every government regulation should be to ensure that the public is protected to the utmost extent possible. The safety of the community is enhanced by earthquake-resistant housing. In light of the fact that the disaster-affected community is now a refugee in another hamlet, the term "protection" must also include "residence status". Alternatively, there are two options. Local residents might either (1) become part of the disaster-affected community or (2) remain confined to their own village. The study's findings were consistent with Kirschenbaum (2004) and Friedman's assertion that community empowerment is best achieved through protection. The community's ability to recover and thrive will be hampered if it is not given adequate protection.

Conclusion

Disaster-affected communities are influenced by self-relocation policies. The Karo community was confronted with a variety of obstacles, including environmental, social, economic, occupational, and cultural changes. The findings of the study revealed one-of-a-kind phenomena. The government permitted the residents of the Mount Sinabung eruption-affected community to choose their own home and agricultural property. The community, on the other hand, elected to construct residential sections and live in groups. Neighbors in the home village were regarded as family members by the community. Living in communities allowed each individual to strengthen and empower one another, accelerating post-disaster recovery. Individual talents also have an impact on community empowerment patterns—each individual can empower themselves by growing self-potential.

Each member of the community participated in a variety of tasks designed to help them develop their own potential, abilities, and skills. Training programs were made available by the government to help people enhance their abilities in the community. The training program, on the other hand, did not completely restore pre-disaster conditions. The government did not carry out an adequate mapping of activity goals and objectives, as required by law. As a result, an in-depth investigation into the training program is required to be conducted. The government will be able to provide proper training programs to the communities as a result of this. The government also failed to offer legal certainty regarding the status of the disaster-affected community's residence. In addition, The relocated community lacked legal certainty regarding the village's citizenship and residency status as a result of the relocation. As a result, it is required to perform a study on the resident status of the disaster-affected community in order to provide proper protection to the community.

References

Ballano, Vivencio O, (2013). Post-disaster Relocation, Housing Project, and Typhoon Ketsana Victims. Law, Normative Pluralism, and Post-Disaster Recovery.

Blanco, Hilda, et al. (2009). "Shaken, Shrinking, Hot, Impoverished and Informal: Emerging Research Agendas in Planning." *Progress in Planning* 72(4): 195–250.

Creswell, John W. (2009). *Research Design Qualitative, Quantitative, and Mixed Methods Approaches*. eds.

Vicki Knight, Sean Connelly, Sarah K. Quesenberry, and Marilyn Power Scott. Los Angeles: SAGE Publication.

Dew, John R. (n.d.) *Empowerment and Democracy in the Workplace*. 10th ed. United States of America: National.

Febriaty, Hastina. (2015). "Dampak Erupsi Gunung Sinabung Terhadap Pendapatan Dari Sektor Pariwisata Di Kabupaten Karo." *Jurnal Ekonomikawan* (September 2010): 53–68.

Freeman, Paul K. (2004). "Allocation of Post-Disaster Reconstruction Financing to Housing." *Building Research and Information* 32(5): 427–37.

Gunawan, Hendra, et al. (2019). "Overview of the Eruptions of Sinabung Volcano, 2010 and 2013–Present and Details of the 2013 Phreatomagmatic Phase." *Journal of Volcanology and Geothermal Research* 382: 103–19. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jvolgeores.2017.08.005>.

Hafni, Roswita, and Lily Suhafni Lubis. (2016). "Dampak Erupsi Gunung Sinabung Terhadap Kondisi Sosial Ekonom Petani Di Desa Suka Meriah Kecamatan Payung Kabupaten Karo Roswita." *Jurnal Ekonomikawan*: 17–31.

He, Lulu. (2019). "Identifying Local Needs for Post-Disaster Recovery in Nepal." *World Development* 118: 52–62. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.worlddev.2019.02.005>.

Hooley, Jill M., and David J. Miklowitz. (2018). *APA handbook of psychopathology: Psychopathology: Understanding, assessing, and treating adult mental disorders* (Vol. 1). Families and Mental Disorders.

Ingram, Jane C., Guillermo Franco, Cristina Rumbaitis del Rio, and Bjian Khazai. (2006). "Post-Disaster Recovery Dilemmas: Challenges in Balancing Short-Term and Long-Term Needs for Vulnerability Reduction." *Environmental Science and Policy* 9(7–8): 607–13.

Islam, M. Rezaul. (2016). *NGOs, Social Capital, and Community Empowerment in Bangladesh*. Singapore: Springer Nature.

Iuchi, Kanako, and John Mutter. (2020). "Progress in Disaster Science Governing Community Relocation after Major Disasters: An Analysis of Three Different Approaches and Its Outcomes in Asia." *Progress in Disaster Science* 6: 100071. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pdisas.2020.100071>.

Jennings, Louise B., Deborah M. Parra-Medina, De Anne K. Hilfinger Messias, and Kerry McLoughlin. (2012). "Toward a Critical Social Theory of Youth Empowerment." *Youth Participation and Community Change* (August): 31–56.

Khasalamwa, Sarah. (2009). "Is 'build Back Better' a Response to Vulnerability? Analysis of the Post-Tsunami Humanitarian Interventions in Sri Lanka." *Norsk Geografisk Tidsskrift* 63(1): 73–88.

Kirschenbaum, Alan. (2004). *Chaos Organization and Disaster Management*. ed. Jack Rabin.

Lord, John, Geoffrey Nelson, and Joanna Ochocka. (2016). *Shifting the Paradigm in Community Mental Health*. Canada: uptpublisiging.

Mannakkara, Sandeeka, Suzanne Wilkinson, and Regan Potangaroa. (2018). *Resilient Post Disaster Recovery through Building Back Better*. Resilient Post Disaster Recovery through Building Back Better.

Manurung, Rudi Kristian, and Februati Trimurni. (2020). "Relokasi Mandiri Permukiman Desa Guru Kinayan Akibat Kejadian Erupsi Gunung Api Sinabung Kabupaten Karo." *Jurnal Administrasi dan Kebijakan Publik* 5(1): 1–21.

Melkote, Srinivas Raj, and H. Leslie Steeves. (2015). *Communication for Development: Theory and Practice for Empowerment and Social Justice*. 3rd ed. India: SAGE Publication.

Miles, Matthew B., A. Michael Huberman, and Jhonny Saldana. (2014). *Qualitative Data Analysis A Methods*

Sourcebook. 3rd ed. eds. Helen Salmon, Kaitlin Perry, Kalie Koscielak, and Laura Barrent. Los Angeles: SAGE Publication.

Mori, Marta, Ronan McDermott, Saut Sagala, and Yasmina Wulandari. (2019). "Sinabung Volcano: How Culture Shapes Community Resilience." *Disaster Prevention and Management: An International Journal* 28(3): 290–303.

Nainggolan, Hotden L Tampubolon, Jongkers, Albina Ginting, Jef R Saragih, and Johndikson Aritonang. (2019). "Livelihood Recovery of a Prolonged Volcano Crisis: Lessons Learned from the Mt . Sinabung Eruption." (February): 1–6.
https://www.researchgate.net/publication/331025336_Livelihood_recovery_of_a_prolonged_volcano_crisis_lessons_learned_from_the_Mt_Sinabung_eruption.

Nainggolan, Hotden Leonardo et al. (2019). "Dampak Erupsi Sinabung Terhadap Kondisi Sosial Ekonomi Petani Hortikultura Di Kecamatan Simpang Empat Kabupaten Karo." *Sosiohumaniora* 21(3): 287–95.

Pallister, John, et al. (2019). "Monitoring, Forecasting Collapse Events, and Mapping Pyroclastic Deposits at Sinabung Volcano with Satellite Imagery." *Journal of Volcanology and Geothermal Research* 382: 149–63.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jvolgeores.2018.05.012>.

Pandia, Stefani Loy, Rini Rachmawati, and Estuning Tyas Wulan Mei. (2016). "Relokasi Permukiman Desa Suka Meriah Akibat Kejadian Erupsi Gunung Api Sinabung Kabupaten Karo." *Jurnal Perencanaan Wilayah dan Kota* 27(2): 137.

Rodwell, Christine M. (1996). "An Analysis of the Concept of Empowerment." *journal of advanced nursing* 23: 305–13.

Sinaga, B., M. Sembiring, and A. Lubis. (2015). "Dampak Ketebalan Abu Vulkanik Erupsi Gunung Sinabung Terhadap Sifat Biologi Tanah Di Kecamatan Naman Teran Kabupaten Karo." *Jurnal Agroekoteknologi Universitas Sumatera Utara* 3(3): 105600.

Sriulina, Indah. (2017). "Pendampingan Pastoral Yang Memberdayakan Penyintas Sinabung Yang Mengalami Trauma." *Indonesian Journal of Theology* 2(5): 147–77.

Suri, Nur Khotimah. (2015). "Analisis Kinerja Badan Penanggulangan Bencana Daerah Kabupaten Karo Dalam Upaya Penanggulangan Bencana Erupsi Gunung Sinabung Di Kabupaten Karo." *Perspektif* 8(1): 456–77.
<https://www.ojs.uma.ac.id/index.php/perspektif/article/viewFile/172/124>.

Tampubolon, Jongkers, H. L. Nainggolan, A. Ginting, and J. Aritonang. (2018). "Mount Sinabung Eruption: Impact on Local Economy and Smallholder Farming in Karo Regency, North Sumatra." *IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science* 178(1).

Tengland, Per Anders. (2008). "Empowerment: A Conceptual Discussion." *Health Care Analysis* 16(2): 77–96.